

A CORRELATION STUDY BETWEEN WORK ENVIRONMENT AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG PRIMARY TEACHER

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Abstract: *The present research deals with Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher. The samples comprise 60 rural and urban Primary Teacher by using Purposive sampling technique. The tools used for present research are Work environment and Job Satisfaction Questionnaire prepared by investigator. The data was analyzed using r .*

Findings

There is significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher.

Keywords: work environment, Job Satisfaction

Introduction:

The concept of work environment is an actual comprehensive one including the physical, psychological and social aspects that mark up the working condition. Work environment performs to have both positive and negative effects on the psychological and welfare of employees. The work environment can be described as the environment in which people are working. Such as, it is very wide category that incorporates the physical scenery.

Employee satisfaction is a function of perceived performance and expectations. It is a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product's outcome to his/her expectations. If the performance falls short

When employees are allowed to operate freely, job satisfaction can contribute substantially to the organizational effectiveness. It can contribute to productive

output in the form of high quantity and quality of products or services, as well as to organizational maintenance as represented by low absenteeism and turnover. Yet in a great many instances, aspects of the individual, the organization, or the environment constrain the satisfaction-productivity relationship to the point where its practical importance is minimal. Ultimately stress may catch up with such a person and signs of poor corporate citizenship may appear, but such denials of natural satisfaction output patterns can maintain themselves for long periods.

Hence the investigators selected the topic Correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher.

Statement of the Problem

"A Correlation study between work environment and Job Satisfaction among Primary Teacher."

Objective

1. To identify the correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher.
2. To identify the correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of male Primary Teacher.
3. To identify the correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of female Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher.
2. There is no significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of male Primary Teacher.
3. There is no significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of female Primary Teacher.

Methodology of the study: Descriptive survey method has been used for the study of the Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher .The sample

comprise for the present study is 60 Primary Teacher. Purposive sampling technique was used to collect the data. The following tools were used to collect the data from Primary Teacher. Work environment and Job Satisfaction Questionnaire prepared by investigator. The obtained data was analyzed by using the Statistical techniques viz. correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation: The collected data is subjected to statistical analysis and the results obtained are as given below.

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher.

Primary Teacher	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Work environment	60	58	.57	.250
	Job Satisfaction				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is .250 and the obtain 'r' value is .57 So the obtain 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtain 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

2 There is no significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of male Primary Teacher.

Male Primary Teacher.	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
	Work environment	30	28	0.54	.361
	Job Satisfaction				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.361 and the obtained 'r' value is 0.54. So the obtained 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtained 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of male Primary Teacher.

Hypotheses:

3 There is no significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Female Primary Teacher.

	Variables	N	df	Obtained 'r'	Table 'r'
Female Primary Teacher.	Work environment	30	28	0.57	.361
	Job Satisfaction				

The table 'r' value at .05 level is 0.361 and the obtained 'r' value is 0.57. So the obtained 'r' value is greater than table 'r' value. So the null hypothesis is rejected. On the basis of obtained 'r' value; we can say that, there is significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of female Primary Teacher.

Findings

1. There is significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher.
2. There is significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of male Primary Teacher.
3. There is significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of female Primary Teacher.

Conclusion

The findings of present study shows that the significant correlation between Work environment and Job Satisfaction of Primary Teacher. Is observed in case male, female Primary Teacher.

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